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SYSTEMIC PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT FOR FAMILIES RAISING CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

Abstract.

The article presents practical work experience implemented in the framework of comprehensive assistance to children with autism spectrum disorder and the families who raise them, and reveals the main activities of the recently opened public association "Support for Children with Autism" in Nakhichevan. The article presented a retrospective analysis of the history of the issue, the contribution of foreign and domestic scientists to the study of this issue, the main problems faced by families, and a proven program to assist this category of families.

Key words: *autism spectrum disorders, comprehensive diagnosis, rapid diagnosis, comprehensive support, family support, support program.*

The problem of providing assistance to families raising a child with an autism spectrum disorder has always been in the focus of attention of scientists, who are still trying to comprehensively approach this problem. The relevance of the topic we are considering is due to a complex of scientific, social, economic and humanistic factors, which makes autism spectrum disorder one of the key challenges for the global health, education and social protection system.

Families raising a child with autism face a number of challenges, including the need for constant support, difficulties in understanding and interacting with the child, as well as high financial and emotional pressures. These families often experience increased stress and need specialized help and support.

Scientific research conducted in modern science is increasingly trying to provide us with new models and programs for working with children with autism spectrum disorder, as well as to coordinate the work of specialists in providing assistance and support to families who have a difficult job on their shoulders. Some aspects of this problem have been the subject of research by foreign researchers N.E.Rosen, K.Lord, F.R.Volkmar [10], E.O'Nions, E. Sulemans, F. Happe [9], I. Feldman, J.Koller, E.R.Lebowitz [12], Turkish [1,2,3] and Azerbaijani specialists L.S.Amrakhly [4], G.A.Hasanova [5,6,7] who worked in this field, presented the results of experimental studies on working with children with autism spectrum disorder, and launched extensive activities to provide social assistance and support to families experiencing difficulties in raising a child with these disorders – S.A.Morozov, S.G. Chigrina [8]. T.M. Verdiyeva the pedagogical and psychological foundations of social adaptation of children and adolescents with autism syndrome were considered [11].

Modern scientists are increasingly turning their attention to the development of new programs that are

not only educational in nature, but also have a significant correctional and developmental effect, which will optimize the process of integrating children of this group into society.

Significant steps have been taken in Azerbaijan in recent years to solve this problem. Centers have been opened that provide assistance to people with this disorder. including rehabilitation centers and medical institutions. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has built an Autism Center in Baku, which has been operating since 2013. In addition, there are medical centers in Baku offering autism treatment services, such as «Biological Medicine-Integrative Health Center» Baku, which is a multidisciplinary medical center specializing in the treatment of autism, centers for speech pathology and psychological assistance, and some medical centers in Baku, such as «Mayomed Medical», «Rahima Atesh» and others offer physical therapy and rehabilitation services for children with autism, and there is a children's psycho-neurological center that can also provide assistance to children with autism spectrum disorder.

An important step has been taken in Nakhichevan towards solving the social problems of this category of children and their families. The public association "Support for Children with Autism" was recently established. The main goal of the public association is to ensure the integration of children with autism into society, facilitating their access to education and medical services, as every child requires special support and love.

In addition, the organization aims to provide psychological support to families, raise awareness of children with autism spectrum disorder, support their education and upbringing, ensure their integration into society and support their families.

To this end, the non-governmental organization Public Association "Support for Children with Autism" has established a system of Honorary and simple membership. Financial resources from these members will be used for the education and therapeutic processes of

children with autism, the organization of activities that support their social and emotional development, as well as the implementation of educational and supportive programs for parents.

As the founder of the Center for Modern Psychology and the public association "Support for Children with Autism", in our activities we try to provide help and assistance not only to parents of children with autism, but also to reveal their special talent, trying to teach others to accept differences as a strength, not as a weakness. We believe that autism is not a disease, but a difference. That is why we plan to implement important projects in this area in this organization.

Let's focus on the problems that families face raising a child with an autism spectrum disorder. The main problems:

- The biggest problem is social isolation and misunderstanding from others, as well as the need for constant child care, which makes social activity difficult;
- Difficulties in understanding and interacting with the child. Behavioral features of children with autism, such as communication difficulties, sensory sensitivity, and emotion dysregulation, create difficulties in daily life and interaction with others;
- Siblings of a child with an autism spectrum disorder also need support, as they may experience conflicting feelings, feel lonely, and have difficulty understanding their sibling's autism;

Emotional and psychological difficulties. Parents of children with autism often experience depression, anxiety, and other mental health problems due to high levels of stress and the need for constant adaptation.

And of course, it should be noted that treatment, therapy and specialized services for children with autism create a significant financial burden on families. Therefore, supporting families raising children with autism requires an integrated approach that takes into account both the psychological and social aspects of family life.

It is important that society, including relatives, friends, and professionals, show understanding and empathy, as well as provide practical and emotional support. Speaking about psychological help, it should be noted how important it is to provide parents with access to psychological support that will help them cope with stress, anxiety and depression, as well as learn how to interact effectively with their child. It is important to create conditions for social activity of families, provide access to information and resources, and promote understanding and acceptance in society. Among the variety of important family support activities, the development and implementation of educational programs and trainings for parents who need to learn the skills necessary to care for a child with autism, as well as information about autism in order to better understand its features, should be particularly noted.

In the public association where we launched activities related to the provision of assistance and support to families, we reviewed the key aspects and areas of this support based on modern approaches. Let's focus on the basic principles:

Fig. 1. Basic principles of family support.

Thus, psychological and pedagogical support for a family raising a child with an autism spectrum disorder is a comprehensive system of measures aimed at in-

creasing not only the internal but also the external resources of the family, developing the competencies of its members and creating optimal conditions for the development of the child himself.

In working with families, we have developed a model based on which we can effectively organize family support work. The main components of this model are the following:

Psychological support for parents:

- Individual and family psychological counseling (CBT, ACT - acceptance and responsibility therapy, short-term strategic therapy);
- Support and mutual assistance groups (offline/online) where experiences and feelings can be safely shared;
- Self-regulation skills training (meditation, mindfulness, breathing techniques);
- Reducing stress, preventing burnout, forming adequate attitudes, strengthening self-confidence through learning new skills and practicing successful actions, working through feelings of guilt, grief, shame, and anger that arise after diagnosis.

Pedagogical support of the child's educational direction:

- Interaction with a school or preschool institution;
- The parent as an intermediary between the family and the educational organization, teaching parents' educational strategies: helping a child with homework, consolidating school skills at home in a playful, everyday way;
- Assistance in adapting the educational program to a specific child;
- Advising teachers on the use of individual approaches, visual support, and sensory load reduction.

Education and formation of parental competencies:

Psychological education about the nature of autism spectrum disorders, strengths, realistic expectations, and erroneous stereotypes;

- Principles and methods of correction of undesirable behavior (functional behavior analysis, development of positive behavioral plans, ABA elements with humanistic ethics);
- Communication development: training in the use of alternative and augmentative communication systems (PECS, gestures, communicators), development of speech comprehension, dialogue skills;
- Formation of self-service and household adaptation skills (schedules, tips, step-by-step training);
- Sensory integration in everyday life: creating an adapted sensory environment at home, recognizing and meeting the sensory needs of the child.

Social and informational support:

- Information: training seminars and workshops, practical skills are developed through trainings, video modeling, homework;
- Supervision: advising parents by a specialist (AVA specialist, defectologist) on the application of strategies in practice at home;
- Organization of inclusive leisure activities;
- Maintaining contacts with other families (creating a community), preparing for going out in public places.

In addition to this model, we have developed a correctional and developmental program, which, based on the analysis of primary diagnostic results, suggests using ABA therapy to increase the level of social and

household skills in children, expand the range of social and household ideas about the world around them, form the foundations of social orientation, create conditions for successful adaptation and socialization in the society of children with ASD, accumulate experience of independent actions in everyday life, instill cultural and hygienic skills and self-service skills, develop attention, memory, thinking, spatial representations, etc.

The experience of psychological and pedagogical correction shows that a specially organized environment can stimulate the development and use of social and household skills by children with ASD.

Of course, this process of mastering and using skills is long and gradual and requires a lot of patience from adults. In addition, a dynamic observation card is issued for each pupil, which records the dynamics of the child's development during classes, the conclusion of specialists with detailed recommendations for the family on further organization of education, upbringing and development of the child, recommendations for obtaining consultations from specialized doctors and specialists from other organizations for further correctional and developmental work..

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